

Deep Echo State Networks for modelling of industrial systems

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Abstract. In the industrial field, the modelling of complex systems is a relevant task to understand their evolution, to infer their most representative characteristics, or to detect anomalous situations. Nevertheless, this modelling is notably challenging within the industrial environment, with large amounts of data to be processed but several difficulties in extracting knowledge from these data.

In this paper, we work with an industrial plant with four water tanks, focusing on estimating the levels of two sequentially connected tanks. For this purpose, Deep Echo State Networks (Deep ESNs), within the framework of Reservoir Computing (RC), are used, representing an increasingly popular methodology for efficient learning to modelling systems with diverse time-scale dynamics.

Specifically, we have designed a learning system that makes use of a dedicated Deep ESN module for the prediction of the level of each tank. We conducted numerical experiments to examine how the performance of the predictions is affected by the number of layers. Our findings indicate that increasing the number of recurrent layers leads to better predictions, and also highlight noteworthy differences in the dynamics of the upper and lower tanks.

Keywords: Reservoir Computing · Echo State Networks · Deep Echo State Networks · Dynamics · Data-based modelling

1 Introduction

Modelling and representing the behaviour of complex systems over time is a task of great relevance in the field of industrial engineering: it can be used to better understand how the modelled physical system works and how it evolves, to know which are its most representative characteristics or to detect anomalous or faulty situations. All of this information leads to an enhancement of efficiency

and an improvement of the performance of the whole process, in the context of an industry that continuously focuses on increasing production and reducing costs [1].

This system representation is particularly challenging when working within the industrial environment, where large amounts of data are acquired from the process, but extracting knowledge of the dynamic behaviour of the process is not that straightforward [17]. Taking into account the need for industrial processes to be increasingly more efficient, better optimised and with more and better functionalities, it is of the utmost importance to achieve a faithful modelling of these processes, by obtaining and representing the aforementioned dynamics.

Machine learning tools are typically used to solve modelling tasks based on this data. More specifically, deep learning models have progressively gained more relevance, mainly due to the possibility they offer to simplify complex machine learning tasks by dividing them into several levels of abstraction [14]. However, the use of these complex architectures implies a higher computational load and a greater time demand for training the models [9].

This drawback is solved by improvements in the hardware with the use of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) and the distribution of the workload, leading to less time-consuming procedures [18]. However, not in all scenarios is it possible to have the necessary hardware resources to run these models, and algorithms with more efficient training are needed.

In this regard, *Reservoir Computing* (RC) [16] is presented as an interesting alternative approach for the design of *Recurrent Neural Networks* (RNNs) through fast and efficient training, with a lower demand on hardware resources [5]. Within RC, one of the most popular models are Echo State Networks (ESNs) [10, 11], in which the reservoir weights are randomly initialised and the only trained layer is a linear readout [20].

With the recently introduced Deep ESNs [6], RC is brought into the world of deep learning, with the development of hierarchical architectures that concatenate several layered reservoirs. These architectures surpass the performance of standard Shallow ESNs by including the representation of multiple time scales from the input data stream [8].

In this paper, we propose the application of Deep ESNs for the modelling of an industrial plant composed of four water tanks, to analyse the improvements in the performance of the models used with the introduction of hierarchical deep RC architectures. Previous work has already tested the performance of Shallow ESNs in the modelling of this four-tank plant [19], and it is of interest to quantify the improvements introduced in the same industrial process with Deep ESNs.

This paper is structured as follows. First, Section 2 introduces reservoir computing and the ESN architectures applied in this paper. Section 3 describes the experimental setup on which the ESN models previously described are applied. Section 4 presents the experiments and the results obtained. Finally, Section 5 brings the conclusions.

2 Reservoir Computing

This section provides an insight into the Reservoir Computing recurrent neural networks applied in this paper. More specifically, Echo State Networks are described as a particular class of RC, with the standard shallow variant in Section 2.1 and its deep RC approach in Section 2.2.

2.1 Shallow Echo State Networks

Fig. 1: Architecture of a Shallow ESN.

Echo State Networks (ESN) [10], as a particular implementation within the Reservoir Computing paradigm, are an efficient approach for modelling *Recurrent Neural Networks* (RNN) [6]. ESNs consist of a static, randomly generated *reservoir* and a trainable *readout*. The reservoir operates based on a random nonlinear recurrent model, which processes an N_U -dimensional vector of input signals $\mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_U}$ into a high-dimensional vector with N_R reservoir states $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$. An interesting and frequently used variation includes a leaky integrator to regulate the recall of the previous states of the ESN [12]. This variant is commonly known as LI-ESN (Leaky Integrator ESN), and it is the architecture used in this work for Shallow ESNs. In a LI-ESN, the state equation of the leaky integrator reservoir units is defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = (1 - \text{lr}) \mathbf{x}(k-1) + \text{lr} \mathbf{tanh}(\mathbf{W}_{res} \mathbf{x}(k-1) + \mathbf{W}_{in} \mathbf{u}(k) + \theta) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ and $\mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_U}$ respectively represent the reservoir and input state vectors at time k , $\mathbf{W}_{res} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$ is the reservoir weight matrix, $\mathbf{W}_{in} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_U}$ is the input-to-reservoir weight matrix, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ is the input bias vector, $\text{lr} \in [0, 1]$ denotes the leaking rate parameter of the leaky integrator, and \mathbf{tanh} is the element-wise application of the activation function (hyperbolic tangent).

The readout function then maps the reservoir states to an N_Y -dimensional vector of outputs $\mathbf{y}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ via a linear model with trainable weights, which

are typically determined using standard least squares methods. The ESN output function is shown in the equation:

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \mathbf{W}_{\text{out}}\mathbf{x}(k) + \theta_{\text{out}} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ is the output at time k , $\mathbf{W}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y \times N_R}$ is the reservoir-to-readout weight matrix and $\theta_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ is the reservoir-to-output bias vector.

The architecture of a Shallow ESN is represented in Figure 1, where bias terms are omitted for simplicity. Architecturally speaking, the echo state network is structured into three layers: the *input* layer, the reservoir itself, and the *readout* or output layer. First, the *input* layer, which is characterized by the matrix \mathbf{W}_{in} , connects the N_I inputs in the input vector $\mathbf{u}(k)$ to the reservoir. Then, the reservoir layer is made up of a substantial number N_R of internal units or *nodes*, with activations or states $x_1(k), \dots, x_{N_R}(k)$, forming the state vector $\mathbf{x}(k)$ at time k . The nodes within the reservoir have feedback and mutual connections, both weighted by the reservoir weight matrix \mathbf{W}_{res} . Finally, the *readout* or output layer, which links the N_R reservoir states in $\mathbf{x}(k)$ to the N_Y outputs in $\mathbf{y}(k)$, based on the weights in the matrix \mathbf{W}_{out} .

The matrices \mathbf{W}_{res} and \mathbf{W}_{in} are constructed using random values, with some adjustments made to promote chaotic dynamics within the reservoir. These random weights are typically sparsified by retaining only a small percentage of random non-zero elements and setting the remaining weights to zero. The reservoir matrix \mathbf{W}_{res} is generally scaled to have its largest eigenvalue ρ_{max} or spectral radius close to 1 (or even slightly above) to maintain the dynamic modes near the edge of stability and satisfy what is called Echo State Property (ESP)[3, 22]. The input matrix \mathbf{W}_{in} is scaled by a given factor is in a range $[-is, is]$.

If the reservoir is applied recursively to an input sequence $\{\mathbf{u}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_K}$, it produces a sequence of high-dimensional state vectors $\{\mathbf{x}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_K}$. Then, these states are combined in the readout with trainable weights to produce the output sequence $\{\mathbf{y}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_K}$. If we arrange the sequences of state vectors and outputs into matrix forms, the output can be obtained as $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{out}}\mathbf{X}$. The readout matrix \mathbf{W}_{out} is usually trained with *ridge regression* method, and it is the approach used in this work.

While there are other configurations and variations of this Shallow ESN model, such as incorporating an output feedback connection by including $\mathbf{y}(k)$ in the reservoir state function (see equation 1), or direct connections from the input to the readout, these will not be discussed here. A more comprehensive and extended insight can be found in [15].

2.2 Deep Echo State Networks

The *Deep ESN* model enables the introduction of ESNs and their advantages in the world of deep learning algorithms. This architecture, which was presented in [6], involves the concatenation of different reservoir layers organised hierarchically so that the first reservoir is fed directly by the input vector, while the

rest of the reservoirs receive as input the output of the previous reservoir (the generated state vector). A representation of the *Deep ESN* architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Architecture of a Deep ESN.

Generally speaking, a set of reservoirs with the same number of units N_R in each one is considered. Thus, for a setup defined with N_L layers, the total amount of units in the hierarchical reservoir architecture is computed as $N_T = N_R \times N_L$.

The state function of the first layer ($l = 1$) is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}^1(k) = (1 - lr^1) \mathbf{x}^1(k-1) + lr^1 \mathbf{tanh}(\mathbf{W}_{res}^1 \mathbf{x}^1(k-1) + \mathbf{W}_{in}^1 \mathbf{u}(k) + \theta^1) \quad (3)$$

while for other layers ($l > 1$) the state equation is given by:

$$\mathbf{x}^l(k) = (1 - lr^l) \mathbf{x}^l(k-1) + lr^l \mathbf{tanh}(\mathbf{W}_{res}^l \mathbf{x}^l(k-1) + \mathbf{W}_{in}^l \mathbf{x}^{l-1}(k) + \theta^l) \quad (4)$$

In these equations, $\mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_U}$ represents the input state vector at time k , $\mathbf{x}^l(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ is the state vector for reservoir at layer l and time k , $lr^l \in [0, 1]$ represents the leaking rate parameter at layer l ; \mathbf{tanh} is the hyperbolic tangent activation function; $\mathbf{W}_{res}^l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$ is the reservoir matrix for layer l ; and \mathbf{W}_{in}^l denotes the input weight matrix for layer l , having $\mathbf{W}_{in}^1 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_U}$ for first layer and $\mathbf{W}_{in}^l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$ for successive layers.

The principle of operation of Deep ESNs is quite similar to that of Shallow ESNs: the reservoirs are initialised following a random uniform distribution, such as $[0, 1]$ and scaled to guarantee certain conditions that keep the system on the edge of stability, and then left untrained. The conditions sought in this case are given by the Echo State Property of Deep ESNs, which is detailed in [4]. It works similarly to the property for Shallow ESNs, likewise looking for the largest eigenvalue ρ_{max}^l to be less than 1 for each reservoir. Similarly, the input matrix

\mathbf{W}_{in} and the connection matrices between reservoirs $\{\mathbf{W}_{in}^l\}_{l=2}^{N_L}$ are generated from a uniform random distribution and scaled in a range $[-is, is]$.

For the calculation of the model output, the most standardised approach is to connect the outputs of all reservoirs to the readout, as can be seen in the schematic in Figure 2. Hence, the network output is obtained according to the following equation, as a weighted sum of the states from the different layers:

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \mathbf{W}_{out}\mathbf{x}(k) + \theta_{out} = \mathbf{W}_{out} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}^1(k) \\ \mathbf{x}^2(k) \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{x}^{N_L}(k) \end{bmatrix} + \theta_{out} \quad (5)$$

Here, $\mathbf{W}_{out} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y \times N_L N_R}$ represents the output weight matrix, the concatenation of the states from all the reservoir layers is $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_L N_R}$, and $\theta_{out} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ denotes the output bias vector.

Deep ESNs have some advantages over Shallow ESNs. To begin with, Deep ESNs are able to generate a representation of multiple time-scale dynamics between the different layers, hierarchically structured so that higher layers have slower dynamics. Furthermore, for the same total number of reservoir units, Deep ESNs have a larger memory capacity than Shallow ESNs, allowing the effect of changes that have occurred earlier in the inputs to be taken into account. In addition, distributing the total number of units among several reservoirs reduces the total number of non-zero recurrent connections, allowing for more efficient operation. Therefore, with the use of Deep ESNs, using the same total number of reservoir units, the overall model performance is considerably improved over Shallow ESNs. Further analysis and details about Deep ESN advantages can be found in [7].

3 Experimentation system

This section describes the environment in which the experiments of the present work have been carried out. In this paper, an experimental setup at the Remote Laboratory of Automatic Control of the University of León is used [2]. This setup is an implementation with real industrial equipment of the four-tank system proposed by Karl Henrik Johansson [13], and it consists of four water tanks arranged vertically in pairs so that the water drained out of the upper tanks ends up in the lower ones. Twin pumps regulated by variable speed drives generate water flow from a lower supply tank to these four tanks.

Water distribution among the tanks is managed by two three-way valves that cross the supplied flows between the tanks. With this system, each pump supplies water to specific tanks, creating a complex control system where the water levels in each tank are influenced not only by pumps and valves but also by the level of other tanks with different dynamics.

Pressure sensors at the base of each tank measure water levels, enabling experiments to control these levels using the aforementioned pumps and valves.

Fig. 3: Industrial plant and its diagram.

Solenoid valves introduce disturbances to the water flow. The implemented industrial plant is illustrated in Figure 3. In addition, the relevant variables that define this plant, such as pump and valve ratios, total pump flow, and tank water levels, are represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables of the quadruple-tank process.

Variable	Units	Description
h_i	0 – 100%	water level in tank i
v_j	0 – 100%	ratio of pump j
$q_{\text{pump},j}$	cm^3/s	total flows of pump j
γ_j	0 – 100%	ratio of valve j

The plant operates as a Multiple Input, Multiple Output (MIMO) system, where pump and valve settings are input variables and desired tank levels are output variables. Alternatively, other scenarios can be explored by treating the plant as Multiple Input, Single Output (MISO) subsystems, focusing on controlling the level of a single tank.

The mathematical model of the four-tank process is derived from Bernoulli's and mass balance laws, resulting in differential equations for each tank's level. A state-space model, commonly used in control engineering, is employed to describe the system. However, implementing theoretical models in real industrial systems like this pilot plant presents challenges due to nonlinearities introduced by industrial equipment, such as sensors noise, nonlinear pump characteristics, and asymmetrical valve responses. These real-world complexities necessitate advanced techniques like machine learning for accurate modelling and control, as linear approaches may lack precision.

4 Experiments and results

This section describes the experiments conducted in this work, the process for hyperparameter selection and the results obtained.

The main objective of this paper is to compare the performance of Shallow ESNs and Deep ESNs in their application to the industrial pilot plant. For this purpose, it is decided to work with two ESN models, which are represented in Figure 3b and are the following ones:

- **Tank 3 MISO model**
 - **Inputs:** Pump 2 rate + Valve 2 position
 - **Outputs:** Tank 3 level
- **Tank 1 MISO model**
 - **Inputs:** Pump 2 rate + Valve 2 position
 - **Outputs:** Tank 1 level

The aim is, for these two defined models, to evaluate their performance depending on the number of reservoir layers used, starting with a single layer, in what would be a standard Shallow ESN, and progressively increasing the number of layers to observe the improvements in network performance and select the number of layers that yields the best results.

This approach is interesting because different time-scale dynamics take place in these two models: as the tanks are connected in series, setpoint changes in pump 2 and/or valve 2 will take longer to be reflected in the lower tank (level 1 modelled by tank 1 MISO model) than in the upper tank (level 3 modelled by tank 3 MISO model). Similarly, more memory capacity will be needed for the lower tank than for the upper tank, and the lower tank will have slower dynamics than the upper tank.

The data used for the model development were obtained from closed-loop experiments with a proportional controller to adjust the tank level with the pump power setpoint. It was decided to work in a closed loop as it is a more faithful recreation of a real industrial plant automation. These experiments had several stages of 60 seconds each, where the controller setpoint, the valve opening percentage, or even both variables simultaneously, were changed. More specifically, these experiments were run for 24 hours, to generate enough random scenarios and obtain enough data to model the industrial plant.

A Python application was used to acquire the data from the plant controller, with a sampling rate of 100 milliseconds, and then the data was resampled to 5 seconds, filtered and split into 60% for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for testing.

The ESN models were programmed, set up and trained using Python and the *ReservoirPy* library [21], a modular library that lets different ESN components as reservoir or readout be parameterized and connected independently. The *hyperopt* library, which is also included in *ReservoirPy*, was used to search and optimize the hyperparameters for the ESN model. It performs a random search within a specified range of values and picks the ones that minimize the model output error.

To evaluate the performance of the Deep ESN models depending on the number of layers, as described above, we proceeded as follows: first, for each number of layers tested, and using the training and validation data, 100 possible combinations of hyperparameters are evaluated using the *hyperopt* library, with several random initialisations for each combination; then, with the hyperparameters that have produced the best results, a new model is generated, trained and tested with the test data. For each number of layers, the errors obtained in validation and test are stored, to later compare the performance of the models according to the architecture design used.

To quantify and compare the errors obtained with the different models, the *Root Mean Squared Error* (RMSE), a frequently used metric to compare observed and predicted values, is used. RMSE is calculated as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{[y(\hat{k}) - y(k)]^2}{n}} \quad (6)$$

where $y(\hat{k})$ and $y(k)$ are, respectively, the estimated and real outputs at sample k , and n is the total number of samples processed. It should be noted that, for the experiments conducted, both outputs of tank levels 3 and 1 are scaled from 0% to 100%.

Table 2: Tested ranges of hyperparameters.

Hyperparameter	Tested values
Total internal units (N_T)	1200
Spectral radius (sr)	0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 1.3
Leaking rate (lr)	10^{-6} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-0}
Input scaling (iss)	1
Inter-layer scaling (ils)	0.1, 0.5, 1, 1.5
Input bias scaling (bs)	0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1
\mathbf{W}_{res}^l connectivity (rc)	0.15
\mathbf{W}_{in}^l connectivity (ic)	0.15
Ridge regularizer (α)	10^{-9} , 10^{-6} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-1}

Following the proposed methodology, and with the data from the dataset described above, the best hyperparameters for each number of layers are sought, according to the values shown in Table 2. Specifically, the best hyperparameters are searched for each number of layers N_L between 1 and 10.

For each combination of hyperparameters tested, the reservoirs in the different layers of the Deep ESN model are initialised with the same hyperparameters, each generated independently and with different random seeds, as usual in experiments with such hierarchical architectures.

To start with, different values for the input bias scaling are tested in the range between 0.2 and 1. In addition, as far as the scaling of the input weight matrices is concerned, there will be a difference depending on the layer: the scaling of the first input weight matrix \mathbf{W}_{in}^1 is set to 1, a value that has worked adequately in previous experiments with Shallow ESNs, while for the scaling of the inter-reservoir matrices $\{\mathbf{W}_{in}^l\}_{l=2}^{N_L}$, different values are tested between 0.1 and 1.5, to evaluate which one produces better results in the model.

Conversely, the connectivity of the reservoir input weight matrices \mathbf{W}_{in}^l , as well as of the reservoir weight matrices \mathbf{W}_{res}^l , are set to 0.15, since this is a value that also tends to yield good results in previous experiments.

Finally, as previous work has shown that the performance of the model is better the higher the number of units in the reservoir, this parameter is left fixed at 1200 at the model level regardless of the number of layers. Thus, the total number of units N_T is divided among all the reservoirs and, if the division is not exact, the remaining units are assigned to the reservoir in the first layer.

Table 3: RMSE on test dataset and best hyperparameters obtained: number of layers (\mathbf{N}_L), input bias scaling (\mathbf{bs}), inter layer scaling (\mathbf{ils}), leaking rate (\mathbf{lr}), spectral radius of reservoir weight matrix (\mathbf{sr}) and readout regularizer (α).

Model	\mathbf{N}_L	\mathbf{bs}	\mathbf{ils}	\mathbf{lr}	\mathbf{sr}	α	RMSE
Tank 3	1	0.4	-	1.0	0.9	10^{-1}	0.0510
	2	0.4	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-3}	0.0519
	3	0.4	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-3}	0.0504
	4	0.4	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-3}	0.0478
	5	0.4	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-3}	0.0467
	6	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0459
	7	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0456
	8	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0470
	9	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0470
	10	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0490
Tank 1	1	1.0	-	1.0	1.3	10^{-6}	0.1070
	2	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.1205
	3	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.1160
	4	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.1012
	5	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0978
	6	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0907
	7	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0827
	8	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0824
	9	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0823
	10	1.0	0.1	1.0	0.9	10^{-6}	0.0837

After applying the proposed methodology to evaluate the performance of Deep ESN models according to the number of layers, the results obtained are shown in Figure 4. This figure presents the evolution of the RMSE as a function of the number of layers, between 1 and 10, for the validation and test data.

(a) RMSE for ESN 3 (level 3 prediction).

(b) RMSE for ESN 1 (level 1 prediction).

Fig. 4: RMSE obtained in validation and test with different number of layers.

The RMSE shown is the average between the executed guesses initialised with different random seeds. The standard deviation of these guesses is also shown. On the other hand, the obtained test RMSE values and the best hyperparameters selected for each number of layers and model are displayed in Table 3. The best RMSE result for each model is highlighted in bold.

Analysing the results it can be seen that, with the same total number of units in the reservoirs N_T , the performance of the models improves significantly as the number of layers increases, reducing the RMSE compared to the Shallow ESN model (where the number of layers N_L is equal to 1). More specifically, Deep ESN is able to improve the predictive performance of Shallow ESN up to approximately 11% in the tank 3 setup, and up to approximately 23% in the tank 1 setup. The improvement by Deep ESN is even more substantial in correspondence of the tank 1 problem, as this corresponds to the case in which the system can benefit more from the presence of the slower dynamics in the reservoir systems.

Furthermore, it can be observed that the best average RMSE is reached with 7 layers for the tank 3 model, while for the tank 1 model it is reached with 9 layers. This confirms that there are different time-scale dynamics in the upper and lower tank levels, as initially deduced. Thus, changes in the pump and/or valve take longer to be reflected in the lower tank than in the upper tank, and more layers with more global memory are needed to obtain a better level prediction in the case of the upper tank.

Finally, as far as the best hyperparameters are concerned (see Table 3), it should be noted that the values obtained are quite similar irrespective of the model applied and the number of layers tested. Therefore, the improvements in the performance of the models are essentially associated with the increase in the number of layers.

5 Conclusions

This work presents an experimental implementation of Deep ESNs in an industrial pilot plant. The industrial plant is composed of four water tanks interconnected with a main water supply regulated by pumps and valves. The purpose of the industrial application is to model the level of the tanks depending on the ratio of pumps and valves. More specifically, two tanks connected sequentially are modelled, knowing that the water flow is delivered with a pump and a valve to the upper tank, and the drainage of this tank ends up in the lower tank.

One model is designed to estimate the level of the upper tank and another one is to predict the level of the lower tank. Deep ESN architectures with different numbers of layers are tested to assess the model performance with hierarchical layouts, looking for the best hyperparameters for each model and a number of layers between 1 and 10.

Based on the results, it can be observed that, with the same total number of reservoir units, increasing the number of layers in the model leads to a significant reduction of the errors given by the predictions. Furthermore, the best

performance for the upper tank is obtained with fewer layers than for the lower tank. These results confirm the expected circumstance of the lower tank having slower dynamics than the upper one, thus requiring more model memory to better estimate the tank level.

Future work will focus on the modelling of the four tanks of the plant as a whole MIMO system, exploring different reservoir layouts and multi-layer hierarchical architectures. Moreover, further analysis of the dynamics that are developed within the different layers of the Deep ESN architectures will be addressed.

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